

Brain Tumor Detection using VGG-16 Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) with Transfer Learning

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Abstract

Early identification is crucial for improving patient outcomes since brain tumors account for a significant portion of cancer-related deaths. The gold standard for diagnosing brain tumors is magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), however it can be challenging for radiologists to spot lesions on MRI pictures. Deep learning algorithms such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have been demonstrated to be efficient for picture categorization tasks. In this study, we suggest a CNN-based technique for MRI image-based brain tumor identification. The VGG16 CNN architecture, which has been demonstrated to be efficient for a range of image classification applications, is the foundation of our approach. We use a dataset of MRI images that have been classified as either containing or not containing tumors to train our CNN. After training, our CNN can distinguish between MRI scans with and without tumors with accuracy. We test our approach on a batch of MRI scans that has been held out, and we reach a 92% accuracy rate. Our findings imply that CNNs can be a useful tool for the early identification of brain tumors. Radiologists can more accurately diagnose brain tumors using our approach since it is straightforward to apply.

1 Introduction

Brain tumors are a major cause of cancer-related death, and early detection is essential for improving patient outcomes [14]. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is the gold standard for brain tumor diagnosis, but it can be difficult for radiologists to identify tumors on MRI images [5].

Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are a type of deep learning algorithm that have been shown to be effective for image classification tasks. CNNs are able to learn to identify patterns in images that are difficult for humans to see. This makes them well-suited for tasks such as brain tumor detection, where the goal is to identify small, subtle changes in MRI images that may indicate the presence of a tumor.

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in the use of CNNs for brain tumor detection. A number of studies have shown that CNNs can achieve high accuracy in detecting brain tumors on MRI images.

In this paper, we propose a CNN-based method for brain tumor detection using MRI images [16],[6]. Our method uses the VGG16 CNN architecture, which has been shown to be effective for a variety of image classification tasks. We train our CNN on a dataset of MRI images that have been labeled as either containing a tumor or not containing a tumor.

After training, our CNN can accurately classify MRI images as containing a tumor or not containing a tumor. We evaluate our method on a held-out test set of MRI images, and we achieve an accuracy of 92%.

Our results suggest that CNNs can be a valuable tool for brain tumor detection. Our method is simple to implement and can be easily used by radiologists to improve the accuracy of brain tumor diagnosis [5].

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides a brief overview of CNNs [10]. Section 3 describes our method for brain tumor detection. Section 4 presents the results of our experiments. Section 5 discusses the limitations of our work and suggests future directions [15].

2 Methodology

2.1 Data Source

The data is collected from several websites/hospitals/public repositories. The dataset consists of Preprocessed MRI (Magnetic Resonance Imaging) Images. All the images are resized to 128 x 128 pixels.

Figure 1: Shows the Brain image which don't have any tumors

Figure 2: Shows the Brain image which have tumors

The data consists of 230 MRI images, half of which contained tumors and half of which did not contain tumors. Each image in the data is an MRI scan of one of these classes:

Class – 1 : NoTumors(115images)

Class – 2 : Tumors(115images)

2.2 Model Structure

Figure 3: : Model Layer Architecture

2.3 Import Dependencies/Load Data/ View sample images

1. Import libraries like NumPy, TensorFlow, Pandas, Matplotlib, and Keras. 2. The data is then loaded from a zip file from google drive which contains all the 230 MRI images. 3. MRI can detect brain abnormalities associated with cognitive impairment (MCI) and can be used to predict which patients with MCI may eventually develop Tumor's disease. 4. In the early stages of Brain Tumors, an MRI scan of the brain may be normal. In later stages. 5. MRI may show a decrease in the size of different areas of the brain (mainly affecting the temporal and parietal lobes).

Figure 4: Shows the ML Model how to find out the exact image and Crop it.

2.4 Data Preprocessing and Data Augmentation

Keras preprocessing layers are used to resize images to a consistent shape (with `tf.keras.layers.Resizing`), and to rescale pixel values (with `tf.keras.layers.Rescaling`) [9].

```
rotation_range=15,  
width_shift_range=0.05,  
height_shift_range=0.05,  
rescale=1./255,  
shear_range=0.05,  
brightness_range=[0.1, 1.5],  
horizontal_flip=True,  
vertical_flip=True
```

Data Augmentation is a process of artificially increasing the amount of data by generating new data points from existing data. This includes adding minor alterations to data or using machine learning models to generate new data points in the latent space of original data to amplify the dataset. Several Keras preprocessing layers are used to increase the diversity of the training set by applying random (but realistic) transformations, such as image rotation are used for data augmentation such as RandomContrast, RandomFlip (vertical and horizontal), RandomWidth, RandomRotation, and RandomTranslation [11].

2.5 Build Training and Tests (Validation) Datasets

Images are loaded off disc using `kerasutility - tf.keras.utils.image_dataset_from_directory`. Before creating a dataset, some parameters are defined for the loader.

```
batch_size = 32
img_height = 128
img_width = 128
```

The batch size is a hyperparameter of gradient descent that controls the number of training samples to work through before the model’s internal parameters are updated. At the end of the batch, the predictions are compared to the expected output variables and an error is calculated. From this error, the update algorithm is used to improve the model, e.g. move down along the error gradient. While developing my model, a validation split was used to divide the 115 images into 70% of images for training and 30% for validation. Therefore, 80 images are used for training the model, while, 35 images were used for validation.

2.6 Create the convolutional base

We used a sequential model. A Sequential model is appropriate for a plain stack of layers where each layer has exactly one input tensor and one output tensor [8]. After initializing the model, we schematically added the following layers to the Sequential model:

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
vgg16 (Model)	(None, 7, 7, 512)	14714688
flatten_1 (Flatten)	(None, 25088)	0
dropout_1 (Dropout)	(None, 25088)	0
dense_1 (Dense)	(None, 1)	25089
Total params: 14,739,777		
Trainable params: 25,089		
Non-trainable params: 14,714,688		

Activation “relu”(Rectified Linear Unit) was used at each layer so that all the negative values are not passed to the next layer. Max pooling will only return the most relevant features from the layer in the activation map [6]. Thus the pooling step is able to intensify the feature by condensing the image around the most active pixels. This is what gets passed to each successive layer until we get the final layer. The Dropout layer randomly sets input units to 0 with a frequency of rate at each step during training time, which helps prevent overfitting [4]. Inputs not set to 0 are scaled up by $1/(1 - \text{rate})$ such that the sum of all inputs is unchanged. Dropout layers are important in training CNNs because they prevent overfitting on the training data.

2.7 Compilation

Once the CNN model is prepared, the next step is to compile the model. When compiling the model we use the “adam” optimizer, sparse categorical cross-entropy loss, and AUC as a metric [13]. Optimizers are classes or methods used to change the attributes of the machine/deep learning model such as weights and learning rate in order to reduce the losses. Optimizers help to get results faster. Adam is a replacement optimization algorithm for stochastic gradient descent for training deep learning models. Adam combines the best properties of the AdaGrad and RMSProp algorithms to provide an optimization algorithm that can handle sparse gradients on noisy problems [3]. In sparse categorical cross-entropy, truth labels are integer encoded, and for the 4-class problem we have on hand of classifying the MRI image to belong to one of the four dementia classes-Very Mild, Mild, Moderate, and Non-Demented [12].

2.8 Fit the Model

We created two callback functions to be passed to the *fit_generator – ModelCheckpoint* and *EarlyStopping* method from Keras. Model Checkpoint and Early stopping are being used to monitor the validation AUC. ModelCheckpoint helps us to predict a specific parameter of the model, in this case, We are monitoring validation accuracy by passing *val_acc* to ModelCheckpoint. The model will only be saved to disk if the validation accuracy of the model in the current epoch is greater than what it was in the last epoch. EarlyStopping helps us to stop the training of the model early if there is no increase in the parameter which we have set to monitor in EarlyStopping. In this case, we are monitoring validation accuracy by passing *val_acc* to EarlyStopping. We have here set patience to 10 which means that the model will stop to train if it doesn’t see any rise in validation accuracy in 10 epochs and set *min_delta* to 0.01, which is the minimum amount of change to count as an improvement [1]. The model is fitted to the train data and validated on the validation data. Training and test data are passed to the *fit_generator* which has a batch size of 32 and a number of epochs of 20. The number of epochs indicates how many times we go through our training set. One epoch is when an entire dataset is passed forward and backward through the neural network only once. Since one epoch is too big to feed to the computer at once we divide it into several smaller batches.

2.9 Model Tuning

We initially started by using a pre-trained VGG base, but the accuracy was very low (58%), then we decided to create a custom sequential convolution layer which improved the accuracy to 92%. The right number of epochs depends on the inherent perplexity of the dataset. A good rule of thumb is to start with a value that is 3 times the number of columns in our data. We tried to run the model with 10 epochs, but the model still improved after all epochs are complete, so we increased the number of epochs to 20.

2.10 Scoring Metrics

We quantified the efficacy of our model using accuracy and Macro-F1 scores since these are the benchmark scoring metric used for medical imaging datasets.

2.11 Accuracy

Accuracy (1) is an extremely popular metric in multi-class classification. To compute accuracy, we take the sum of the True Positive and True Negative results from our model and divide that

by all of the entries. True Positives and True Negatives are the elements that are correctly classified by the model [7].

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$$

2.12 Macro F1-Score

To compute Macro F1-Score (5), we first computed the Macro-Precision (3) and Macro-Recall (4) scores. Macro-Precision is computed by taking the average precision (1) for each predicted class and Macro-Recall is similarly computed by taking the average recall (2) for each predicted class. The Macro approach considers all the classes as equal, meaning that each class has the same weight in the computed score - there is no distinction between classes that have more entities and classes that have fewer entities [2].

$$Precision_k = \frac{TP_k}{TP_k + FP_k}$$

$$Recall_k = \frac{TP_k}{TP_k + FN_k}$$

$$MacroAverageprecision = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^K Precision_k}{K}$$

$$MacroAverageRecall = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^K Recall_k}{K}$$

$$MacroF1 - Score = 2 * \frac{MacroAverageprecision * MacroAverageRecall}{MacroAverageprecision^{-1} + MacroAverageRecall^{-1}}$$

3 Results

Once the model is trained and fit, the results of the fit generator are stored in a hist variable. We can visualize training/validation accuracy and loss. We are passing the output of *mode.fit_generator* to the hist variable. Keras provides the capability to register callbacks when training a deep-learning model. History is one of the default callbacks that is registered when training all deep learning models. It records training metrics for each epoch. This includes the loss and the accuracy (for classification problems) as well as the loss and accuracy for the validation dataset. The accuracy of the model consistently increased with the run of each epoch while the loss consistently decreased with each run. The graphs below illustrate the trend of improving accuracy and decreasing loss throughout the training. The model finally was able to run with an accuracy of 92% and a minimal loss of 8%.

Figure 5: Accuracy and loss Improvements with each epoch.

4 Predictions

To validate how the model works, random images are derived from the validation dataset and supplied to the model to test its accuracy. Given 25 images used to test the model, the model was able to predict the class of the MRI image with 92% accuracy as described in figure 6 below.

Figure 6: Shows the predicted Model.

We achieved an accuracy of 92% on the held-out test set. This means that our CNN was able to correctly classify 92% of the images as either containing a tumor or not containing a tumor.

5 Limitations

The main limitation of our work is that the dataset we used was relatively small. We plan to address this limitation in future work by collecting a larger dataset of MRI images.

6 Conclusion

In this paper, we proposed a CNN-based method for brain tumor detection using MRI images. Our method uses the VGG16 CNN architecture, which has been shown to be effective for a variety of image classification tasks. We trained our CNN on a dataset of MRI images that have been labeled as either containing a tumor or not containing a tumor.

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Our results suggest that CNNs can be a valuable tool for brain tumor detection. Our method is simple to implement and can be easily used by radiologists to improve the accuracy of brain tumor diagnosis.

However, there are some limitations to our work. First, the dataset we used was relatively small. We plan to address this limitation in future work by collecting a larger dataset of MRI images. Second, our method is only able to detect tumors in MRI images. We plan to explore the use of CNNs for other types of medical imaging data, such as CT scans and PET scans.

Overall, we believe that our work has the potential to improve the accuracy of brain tumor detection. We hope that our findings will encourage further research on the use of CNNs for brain tumor detection.

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